

The effect of weather on the spread of malaria mosquitoes using NetLogo agent based modeling

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Abstract— Malaria is an infectious disease caused by the Plasmodium parasite that lives and multiplies in human red blood cells, transmitted by female malaria (anopheles) mosquitoes, in this study a simulation of malaria spread using NetLogo. NetLogo is agent-based modeling, agents here are in the form of mosquitoes and humans. In addition, the environment is also included in the factors that affect the spread such as temperature and humidity. On the results of the implementation, the results of the comparison are obtained between infected humans and vulnerable humans. Likewise, the comparison of infected mosquitoes and vulnerable mosquitoes.

Keywords: malaria, NetLogo, Agent Based Modeling, malaria spread.

I. INTRODUCTION

Malaria is an infectious disease caused by the Plasmodium parasite that lives and multiplies in human red blood cells, transmitted by female malaria (anopheles) mosquitoes, can attack all men and women in all age groups of infants, children and adults. In Indonesia, recorded in 2017 the number of Malaria cases reached 261,617 people in Indonesia [1]. Therefore, monitoring is needed every year to control the spread. This simulation is expected to be used to control the spread of malaria so that it can be used for prevention such as fogging, vaccination, improving health facilities, counseling and so on.

The simulation used here is using NetLogo, which is an open source platform that is useful for agent-based modeling. On NetLogo there is a library for epidemic simulations, but it only occurs between humans and humans without any intermediaries. So, here is also added a new agent namely "mosquito" as an intermediary for malaria.

The purpose of this study is how to build a spread model of Malaria using NetLogo, Analyze the events that occur in the process of spreading Malaria, conclude and evaluate the results of the simulation obtained.

As a limitation of the research here is the object / agent here only humans and mosquitoes. The parameters used here are

weather (temperature and humidity) and demography (population growth rate). Modeling only uses NetLogo and health data follows those in the Indonesian health profile 2017.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. The Process of spreading malaria

Figure 1 Diagram of the spread of malaria through mosquitoes

In Figure 1, malaria transmission occurs only if there are mosquitoes infected with the anopheles virus biting healthy humans, so that if humans infected with the anopheles virus are bitten by healthy mosquitoes, then the mosquitoes become infected by the anopheles virus, and so on.

B. Effect of climate on mosquitoes

Temperature has an influence on the behavior of mosquitoes [2] [3], this can be seen in Table 1

Table 1
Effect of temperature on the behavior of mosquitoes.

Range (°Celsius)	Mosquito Behavior
$0 \leq \text{temperature} \leq 10$ and $\text{temperature} > 39$	inactive
$10 < \text{temperature} < 20$	Random fly
$20 \leq \text{temperature} \leq 39$	Random flying, biting
$25 \leq \text{temperature} \leq 27$	Reproduction
$\text{temperature} < 0$ and $\text{temperature} > 41$	Die

Besides the temperature of humidity also affects the behavior of mosquitoes [4] [5], as shown in Table 2.

Table 2
Effect of humidity on the behavior of mosquitoes

Humidity	Behavior
Humidity > 70	Reproduction, random flying, biting
Humidity ≥ 60	Random fly
Humidity < 60	die

In Table 1 and Table 2 it can be seen that temperature and humidity affect the behavior of mosquitoes, which from these behaviors will be included in the attributes of the mosquito agent.

III. METHODE

A. Data Collection

In this study there were 2 data taken, namely Malaria incident data obtained from the 2017 Health Service report. And climate data in the form of temperature and humidity were obtained from BMKG.

B. Design

The design is done using Netlogo, in the Netlogo two agents will be created, namely mosquitoes and humans, each of which has attributes. The attributes of each agent are shown in Table 3.

Table 3
Attribute of each agent

Agent	Attribute	Information
Mosquito	No nyamuk	Identity number of each mosquito
	Umur	Age of Mosquitoes that have a maximum age of 33 days
	Status	Mosquitoes have health status between vulnerable or infected
	energi	When infected with mosquito energy there are 3 days left (259200 seconds) [6]
	Fertilisasi	Mosquitoes can only reproduce 4 times during their lifetime
	Posisi	Coordinates of the place where the mosquito is located
Human	no_manusia	Identity number for each human
	Umur	Humans have a maximum age of 70 years (BPS)
	Status-kesehatan	Infection occurs when humans are susceptible to being

posisi
infected with a virus by being bitten by an infected mosquito
The position or coordinates of the place where humans are

In addition, each agent is given a behavior, to see the relationships between agents on NetLogo simulations. For the behavior of each agent shown in Table 4.

Table 4
Behavior of each agent

Agent	Attribute	Information
mosquitoe	Menggigit	Mosquitoes will bite humans if energy reaches half the maximum energy [6]
	Menyebarkan virus	If the mosquito has been infected with the anopheles virus, and is > 12 days old, it is able to spread the virus to humans (jacintho et al. 2010)
	Terbang	Fly to move position coordinates
	Reproduksi	Once laying eggs, mosquitoes can produce 100 eggs, assuming 10% are capable of transmitting
Human	Bergerak	Cause to move coordinates
	Lahir	Addition of human population
	Mati	Reduction of human population

Furthermore, a diagram of the spread of malaria can be obtained on mosquito agents as a process that runs on the simulation, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 State diagram of a mosquito agent

Based on Figure 2, mosquitoes that are made to move randomly, under certain conditions will bite humans and under certain conditions will also produce. For the requirements of mosquitoes to produce can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Diagram of reproduction activity of mosquitoes

In Figure 3 shows that mosquitoes reproduce if a mosquito has more than 12 days of age, and at a temperature of 25-27 degrees Celsius, and if the mosquito has not reproduced more than 4 times, and has enough energy. When mosquitoes reproduce, fertility increases by 1.

Figure 4 Diagram of behavior of biting mosquitoes

In Figure 4 shows the condition of mosquitoes doing bites, mosquitoes must be more than 12 days old and in a state of hunger or in minimal energy conditions, besides that it must also be in conditions of temperatures of 20 - 39 degrees Celsius and there are humans near mosquitoes to bite. When mosquitoes bite humans, the mosquito's energy increases by 86400.

Figure 5 Diagram of malaria spread activity

Figure 5 shows the activity of mosquitoes after biting humans, if the human is infected with malaria, the mosquito is infected and dies within 3 days. Whereas if the mosquito is infected and bites a healthy human, then the human has an infected status and will do recovery after 7 days which is assumed to be 95% of the total will recover while the rest die.

C. Implementation

Next to implement the Netlogo, the parameters used here are the number of mosquitoes, the number of people, the level of infection, and the rate of population growth. For the results of implementation through NetLog, can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6 implementation of the spread of Malaria using NetLogo

D. Evaluation

For evaluation we will test our implementation by entering the following parameters, namely for initial-mosquito value 20,

initial-human value of 100, infection-rate value of 59.00 and human-rate of 0.0319. The results are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 Simulation results using NetLogo

Seen in Figure 7, the comparison of humans between those who are vulnerable and those infected is inversely proportional, because if more and more of a population is infected, the more vulnerable the population is infected.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the implementation carried out on NetLogo a graph from the plot results can be seen in Figure 8.

Figure 8 Graph of comparison of humans who are vulnerable to those infected

Figure 8 is taken based on temperature 24 and humidity 85. Seen in the graph that infected humans are inversely proportional to vulnerable humans. Because indeed more and more humans are infected, the vulnerable human population will decrease.

In addition to human studies also compared to humans, a comparison was also made of mosquitoes shown in figure 9

Figure 9 Graph of comparison of vulnerable mosquitoes to those infected

Seen in Graph 9 the comparison of vulnerable mosquitoes with infected ones, was tested for 30 days at 24 degrees Celsius, where mosquitoes were flying and biting but did not reproduce, on days 1 to 8 the infected mosquitoes decreased, because the infected mosquitoes will die after 3 days and here the mosquitoes are not in the reproductive period, so that the initial mosquitoes which amount to 50 will run out within 30 days if the temperature is 24 degrees Celsius which lasts for a month.

The next test is to change the temperature and humidity to 26 and 85, which is where mosquitoes in addition to biting also experience reproduction at the temperature and humidity, and the results obtained as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 Comparison of vulnerable people with humans infected with malaria at a temperature of 26 degrees Celsius

Tests were carried out for two months and the results showed that the number of infected humans increased continuously so that the population of 100 initially contracted malaria as a whole on the 50th day if it was 26 degrees Celsius where at this temperature mosquitoes experience reproduction. In the graph also obtained a formula for comparison of vulnerable humans, namely $y = 2.1179x - 11,361$ and infected humans, namely $y = -2.0791x + 111.78$

As for how vulnerable and infected the mosquito population is when the temperature allows the mosquito to reproduce, the results are shown in figure 11

Figure 11 Comparison of vulnerable mosquitoes and infected mosquitoes at 26 degrees Celsius

In Figure 11 it can be seen that the vulnerable and infected mosquitoes experienced a significant increase, for 2 months the mosquitoes which initially numbered 50 could increase by almost 1000 mosquitoes, while those infected could be more than 600 mosquitoes, this occurs if the temperature is 25-27 degrees Celsius continues for 2 months. The graph also shows the formula obtained for infected mosquitoes: $y = 6.8556e.0801x$ and for vulnerable mosquitoes $y = 12.533e0.0632x$.

V. CONCLUSION

Agent-based modeling uses NetLogo to simulate the spread of Malaria with influencing temperature and humidity. Seen in the results of the test, the ratio of infected humans is inversely proportional to susceptible humans, as well as the ratio of mosquitoes infected with vulnerable mosquitoes. If during the reproduction period of mosquitoes, which is 24-27 degrees Celsius for more than 2 months, mosquitoes develop up to 20 times the initial amount. It is expected that in the future testing will be carried out with input temperature that changes on its NetLog, so that it can be compared with the actual results that this simulation is in accordance with the actual conditions or not.

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